

Credentials and Proofs of Certificates

- User Manual -

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1. Introduction

The functionality of checking Credentials and Proofs of Certificates in MEDINA is provided by the *Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework* tool. The *SSI Framework* provides Cloud Service Providers (CSPs) with the capability to manage their own security certificates as part of their identity through verifiable credentials. “To manage their own identity” ultimately means that they store their identity on their own “user space” without intervention of a third-party.

The *SSI Framework* is not only composed of the CSP component to store and control its own credentials. It is also composed of the *Issuer* component, which provides Conformance Assessment Bodies (CABs) a way to issue verifiable credentials about the security certificates related to the CSPs; and the *Client* component, which provides a way to ask and verify proofs of different security certificates features. In this sense, privacy is an important requirement within MEDINA, as several security certificates features are considered sensitive and must be treated carefully. The *SSI Framework* is capable of sharing sensitive information in a confidential way by keeping the user’s identity out of the reach of third parties, that act as identity silos, reducing the risk of identity theft; but also by using Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs).

1.1. User Roles and Permissions

Access to the *SSI Framework* is managed by Keycloak¹. The visibility of the different elements of the *Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework*, and the operations that are allowed to be carried out are conditioned by the role to which each authenticated user is assigned.

The table below details which actions are allowed for each of the defined roles:

Roles	Allowed Actions
IT Security Governance	Read credentials and proofs
Security Analyst	None
Domain Governance	Read credentials and proofs
Product and Service Owner	None
Product (Security) Engineer	None
Chief Information Security Office (CISO)	Read credentials and proofs
Customer	Read proofs
Auditor	Read credentials and proofs, Issue credentials

¹ <https://www.keycloak.org>

2. User Manual

2.1. Toolbar

The *Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework* includes a toolbar (see Figure 1), always accessible in the upper area, with all the options that are available in the tool:

Figure 1. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework toolbar

The different menu options, which are described in the following sections, are as follows:

- **Certificate Credentials Lifecycle:** Provides contextualization information for a better understanding of the tool operation.
- **Certificate Credentials:** Provides access to the list of stored verifiable credentials about the security certificate status of the CSP'S Cloud Services
- **Certificate Proofs:** Provides access to the list of the proof requests received about the security certificate status of the CSP'S Cloud Services.
- **Help:** Provides access to the user manual of the tool.
- **Administration:** Provides access to information on connections. This option is only available to users with administration rights.

2.2. Certificate Credentials Lifecycle

The *Certificate Credentials Lifecycle* view (see Figure 2) provides an overview of the tool's components and operation for a better understanding of the tool.

Figure 2. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework context

As a summary, the *SSI Framework* is composed of three main components:

- Certificate signing graphical application for the CAB: to issue, update, or revoke security certificates of a CSP'S Cloud Service based on the updated certificate state received from the *Automated Certificate Lifecycle Manager*² component.

² For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D4.3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927231>

- Graphical application for the CSPs: to save the signed security certificates as well as to generate verifiable proofs based on them. This application has been integrated in the *MEDINA Integrated UI*.
- Graphical application for CSP clients: to request and verify proofs of security certificates.

2.3. Certificate Credentials

The *Certificate Credentials* view provides a list of the existing certificate credentials of the Cloud Services in the CSP. The complete list of security credentials received appears as shown in Figure 3. The certificate credentials can be copied or removed using the buttons on the right.

Figure 3. SSI Framework security credentials list

2.4. Certificate Proofs

The *Certificate Proofs* view provides a list of the received certificate proofs of the Cloud Services in the CSP. The complete list of certificate proofs received appears as shown in Figure 4. The certificate proofs can be copied or removed using the buttons on the right.

Figure 4. SSI Framework security proofs list

2.5. Administration

The *Administration* view provides a way for administrators to correctly configure the *SSI Framework* to work with other SSI agents (issuer and verifier).

2.5.1. Connections

The *Connections* view provides a way to list existing connections, as shown in Figure 5, as well as to create new connections to other SSI agents (issuer and verifier), if needed. This option is only available to users with administration rights.

Figure 5. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework existing connections

The required connections are set by default. However, if new connections are needed, they can be created via the *Create Connection* button. A new entry will then appear in the list. This new entry includes the *Share*, *Download* and *Remove* button.

Clicking on the *Share* button, a dialog box will be opened as shown in Figure 6. This dialog box contains a QR code with the invitation that the other party can scan to comfortably enter the invitation. Apart from that code, a *Copy to clipboard* button will allow to copy the invitation to the clipboard.

Figure 6. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework sharing connection

The user who is going to use this invitation to open a new connection to the former SSI agent will have to enter it manually (as shown in Figure 7) or simply scan it from its browser if both users are in the same location. The invitation can be shared using any external secure communication mechanism, such as email or SMS.

Figure 7. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework connection definition

Any SSI-agent will automatically accept the invitation and complete the invitation procedure. Eventually both the invitation sender and receiver will see the new connection listed and marked as “completed”, as shown in Figure 5.

3. Certificate Credentials Issuance (CAB)

In addition to the graphical application for the CSPs integrated in the *MEDINA Integrated UI* described in Section 2, there is also an additional graphical UI for the CAB to issue new certificate credentials, which is available at: <https://medina-webapp.cybersec.digital.tecnalia.dev/>.

The first thing the webapp asks the user to do is to connect to one of the available SSI-agents. In this case, the “Issuer” agent must be selected, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework external connection page for issuer

Once connected, the most interested webapp page for the CAB is related to the “Certificate Credentials”, where new certificate credentials can be issued through the *Create Credential* button. Automatically, a form like the one in Figure 9 is displayed.

The screenshot shows a form titled 'Send credential auto-offer'. Below the title is the instruction: 'Fill the information below to create a new credential.' The form contains three main sections: 1. 'Connection' with a dropdown menu showing 'MEDINA SSI Tecnalia Holder (7c96ba91-cea0-42e2-a020-28c440460031)'. 2. 'Owned schema' with a dropdown menu showing 'J3t3dq1f3PT3yjBEFeqxHT:3:CL:2609:default (version 1.0)'. 3. 'Attributes' with two text input fields: 'cloud_service_id' containing '0001' and 'certificate_status' containing 'done'. At the bottom right, there are two buttons: 'CANCEL' and 'ACCEPT'.

Figure 9. Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework certificate credential issuance

The required details are as follows:

- **Connection:** to whom the credential is to be issued. By default, “MEDINA SSI Tecnalia Holder TEST” should be selected.
- **Owned schema:** the specific format considered for the credential. By default, medina-ssi (version 1.0).

- **Attributes** (id, status): these will be automatically completed every time new information is received from the *Certificate Lifecycle Manager*³ (LCM), i.e., every time the LCM detects a change on the certificate status.

³ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D4.3 <https://zenodo.org/record/7927231>

4. Certificate Proofs Request (CSP Customer)

The *SSI Framework* provides a potential customer (or other entity) with a graphical interface to asks for proofs of the certificate status of the CSPs. It is available at: <https://medina-webapp.cybersec.digital.tecnalia.dev/>.

The first thing the webapp asks the user to do is to connect to one of the available SSI-agents. In this case, the “Verifier” agent must be selected as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. SSI Framework external connection page for verifier

Once connected, the most interesting webapp page for customers is related to the “Certificate Proofs”, where new certificate proofs can be requested through the *Request Proofs* button. Automatically, a form like the one in Figure 11 is displayed.

Figure 11. SSI Framework certificate proofs request

The required details are as follows:

- **Connection:** to whom the proofs will be requested. By default, “MEDINA SSI Tecnalia Holder TEST” should be selected.

- **Comment:** comment for the proof (the reason of the proof could be provided). This is a text parameter.
- **Attributes:** list of the attributes the verifier wants to know about the Cloud Services in the CSP. In MEDINA there are only two attributes (id and status). Any of them (or both of them) should be included. If a different attribute is provided, the process works but the proof will be finally abandoned as the CSP cannot probe the required information.
- **Conditions:** this is an optional parameter related to the ZKP (Zero Knowledge Proof) concept. For example, an attribute such as “postcode” could be considered in this case to indicate a geographical area without disclosing the exact location. This is not really applicable in MEDINA although it can be verified with the id attribute.

Once requested, the new request will be automatically shown in the certificate proofs list on the CSP *SSI Framework* (see section 2.4 for more details), and will also be automatically included in the proofs list on the webapp, obtaining the requested values and indicating the “done” state (shown in green in Figure 12). Additionally, it is also shown as “verified” if the credential has not been revoked.

Certificate Proofs

Ask for proofs and query them in the identity provider **Verifier**.

[REQUEST PROOFS](#)

Proof id:	41faa0cc-406d-442a-9202-0e46a1910e0d	
Created at:	2023-07-28T07:20:28.599835Z	
Updated at:	2023-07-28T07:20:29.194056Z	
Req. comment:	Example of proof	
Pres. comment:	auto-presented for proof requests, pres_ex_record: 1b369711-9734-4f4a-b45e-9facc8cc2113	
Attributes:	certificate_status: done	

done Role: verifier Verified

Figure 12. SSI Framework certificate proofs response

5. Delivery and usage

5.1. Licensing information

This component is offered under Proprietary License. Copyright by TECNALIA.

5.2. More information

Interested readers can find more information about the *Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework* at this link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927231> “D4.3 Tools and Techniques for the Management and Evaluation of Cloud Security Certifications – v3”.

The MEDINA web site (<https://medina-project.eu/>) also includes several deliverables and blog posts related to the *Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Framework*.